

The ATLAS/Brazil Cluster: Current Status and Perspectives from the ATLAS Upgrade Programme

Summary

The ATLAS/Brazil Cluster started research activities at CERN in 1988, when new detector technology was being developed envisaging future collider experiments. The ATLAS collaboration was formed as the sequence of successful R&D projects. Thus, this research team is in ATLAS since its conceptual design. Currently, the ATLAS collaboration is investigating the upgrades required to prepare the experiment for the start of operation of the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC). As a general-purpose experiment, the goal is to increase the likelihood of observing the different physics models being evaluated in the LHC. Several detector components must be replaced to cope with the vertiginous increase in luminosity. In this context, the calorimetry system will undergo major changes in its electronics, the event filtering system will also undergo profound changes in the information used and its algorithms and the reconstruction of events will become quite complex due to the enormous increase in detector occupancy and the consequent signal pileup effects. In all these aspects the ATLAS/Brazil Cluster has research work being developed now, so that there is a deep involvement of this team on the ATLAS upgrade programme. Additionally, the Cluster is responsible to develop and maintain a significant number of ATLAS management systems, which are based on GLANCE/FENCE technology originally developed at UFRJ.

Introduction

ATLAS is the largest of the LHC experiments and is capable of covering a broad physics programme. ATLAS comprises different sub-detectors (tracking system, electromagnetic calorimetry - Liquid Argon calorimeter, Lar, and hadronic - scintillating tile calorimeter, TileCal is the main hadronic, and muon spectrometer). Moreover, as the event rate

to be analyzed is very high (one collision every 25 ns) and the detector segmentation very thin (which generates a special big data case, producing an information rate of 60 TB/s), ATLAS relies on a sophisticated online event filtering (trigger) system, which retains the signals of interest and rejects background noise events as much as possible. It is important to note that ATLAS played an important role in the experimental confirmation of the Higgs boson, a discovery that was awarded with the 2013 Nobel Prize in Physics.

Brazil has been participating in ATLAS since its conception, starting in 1988, through a pioneering initiative by UFRJ, which allowed the formation of the so-called ATLAS / Brazil Cluster, composed by physicists, engineers and computer technicians from UERJ, UFBA, UFJF, UFRJ, and USP. Throughout all these years, a significant number of PhDs and Masters have been formed in this environment. Many of these graduates presently work at different national and foreign companies (Embraer, Petrobras, IBM, National Instruments, Philips, among others) and universities and research institutes (Cluster universities, CBPF, IEAv, CEFET, Idiapi - Switzerland, Brookhaven - USA, among others). Besides, several of these researchers continue to work in the field of high energy experimental physics, which produces a very active research network centered on the ATLAS / Brazil Cluster. This research network has also collaborated in the aspects of scientific dissemination and improvement of high school and technological education in experimental physics and associated technology through a number of initiatives (developing reference material in Portuguese, a Web TV channel, giving lectures in different schools of Rio de Janeiro and other Brazilian states, organizing virtual visits to ATLAS and Masterclasses for data analysis).

It is worth to mention that the Brazilian industry has been participating in the construction of ATLAS, from two electronic circuit boards designed by the Cluster and produced in Brazil, which were both operating in the ATLAS trigger system up to the end of the Run 2 data acquisition in 2018. The innovation aspects in the work developed at ATLAS led to

the creation of six technology-based companies native to COPPE, which today, in addition to their current operation in the market, still work together with the ATLAS / Brazil Cluster and with activities supported by CERN.

Currently, the ATLAS collaboration is running an extensive upgrade programme, in order to be prepared for the start of operation of the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC). The ATLAS upgrade programme has still two phases to be completed. During the present shutdown, which is planned up to 2021, the luminosity peak will correspond to 55-80 25 ns interval collision interactions. Several upgrades will be required in this phase and should already be fully compatible with the HL-LHC physics program. Next phase upgrades are expected to handle up to 200 interactions. For this, the final versions of detector components should be installed.

The ATLAS upgrade programme for the HL-LHC presents several research challenges with respect to instrumentation, signal processing, software, and increases new physics discovery possibilities. The higher radiation levels and data rates that the new front-end and back-end electronics have to cope with require the use of new and advanced electronics for the detectors. Sophisticated signal processing techniques such as blind source separation, adaptive filtering and deconvolution methods should be considered for energy estimation in high luminosity scenario. Similarly, the trigger system requires new electronics and complex algorithms to keep up with the desired performance for high luminosity.

In terms of calorimetry, the Cluster is involved in both electronic instrumentation and algorithm development. The activities aim at developing the new back-end electronics (FPGA-based) and new energy estimation algorithms based on deconvolution strategies to be used both online and offline. Additional (level one) trigger from the Tilecal last segmentation layer is currently being provided for the extended barrel part of ATLAS and may also cover the barrel, so that muon trigger may be assisted from Tilecal information. Still within Tilecal, an

effort is being made for providing finer granularity through a multianode PMT readout. The aim is to achieve two or four times finer detector cell granularity without changing the mechanical structure of the calorimeter. Computational intelligence and blind source separation techniques are being used envisagem operation in the second upgrade phase. Concerning the e.m. calorimeter (Lar), activities are mainly related to the implementation of the Super Cells, which refer to a new trigger piece of hardware. Additionally, signal processing and machine learning techniques are being applied for cross-talk mitigation. For the triggering system, we are participating in the development of new computational intelligence based techniques for the calorimeter high-level trigger (HLT) system, which are also to be extended to the offline filtering. Besides, efforts are being made to improve the trigger calibration for electrons. Possible extensions of the machine learning techniques developed for HLT to level-one triggering (embedded electronics) are also being pursued (FPGA-based designs). Concerning the physics analysis, activities include the search for ALP (Axion Like Particle) and Standard Model analysis.

The ATLAS management has mainly been structured upon the Glance/FENCE technology, which was developed by the ATLAS/Brazil Cluster. The success of this technology made other LHC experiments (ALICE and LHCb) to be interested in applying it to their systems, so that today this technology is supporting their management activities as well. Upgrades on GLANCE/FENCE are also being made in order to evolute the technology towards the HL-LHC requirements.

The upggrade activities strengthen the participation of our cluster in ATLAS and are built upon our excellent collaboration insertion and previous experience with respect to Brazilian industry participation during ATLAS construction, which will be enlarged in terms of hardware and software. Technology based companies from Brazil (some of them formed along this long-term work in ATLAS) will benefit from this new working period at CERN and new

companies may also be created and consolidated. Additionally, this upgrade effort will also foster the technology spinoffs of the techniques and processes developed for ATLAS in this extremely high demanding HL-LHC framework to other areas, as it has successfully been done along these years of Brazilian participation in ATLAS (in medicine, oil & gas, among other areas). The opportunity for research in the ATLAS upgrade programme will also allow the formation of high-quality manpower at the various levels of education.